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PEM Fuel Cell Analysis Completed

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Abstract

In 1837 my great-great-grandfather Christian Friedrich Schoenbein discovered the fuel cell effect. At that time the understanding of electrochemical phenomena was at an early stage. The overall chemical combination in fuel cells of hydrogen and oxygen to water was evident, but 187 years later the analysis is still focused on the search for an equilibrium potential of 1.23V and four electrons predicted for the complete hydrogen oxidation to water. I grew up with the information that Schoenbein had discovered ozone and invented gun cotton. But at the first Grove fuel cell seminar I attended John Appleby presented a list of early publications on the subject. Schoenbein was listed five times while Grove only twice. This excited my interest in the history of fuel cells. The summary of my researches has recently been published. "Fuel Cells – from Birth to Maturity" [1] presents the history of the fuel cell discovery between 1835 and 1845. The complete correspondence between Schoenbein and Grove is published for the first time and an analysis is presented for the startup phase of proton-conducting fuel cells. Apparently the practiced fuel cell analysis needed a number of corrections. There are two electrochemical reactions to be considered. Also, the number of polarity shifts of electrons is missing in the equilibrium potential equation. With these corrections the experimental evidence can be brought to a perfect agreement with theory. The experimental discovery of Christian Friedrich Schoenbein is explained 197 years later by his great-great-grandson. This appears to be a unique case of science history. Fuel cells have become a family affair.

1. Good Experiments, but Shaky Theory

Within seven years from Schoenbein’s discovery 1838 to Grove’s patent-like presentation of 1845 fuel cells have evolved from innovation to demonstration without a convincing base of understanding, as science was still philosophy. Neither Schoenbein nor Grove or anyone else was able to correctly relate the fuel cell effect to the laws of nature. The fuel cell effect was explained by speculative assumptions. Important details of physics and chemistry were later identified and added to the inventory of science. But the early interpretations were soon accepted and passed from teachers to students and from textbook to textbook. Fuel cell scientist preferred to confess that they are searching for a way to explain the predicted open circuit voltage of 1.23 Volt that had never been observed. The widely accepted understanding of proton-conducting fuel cells is illustrated by Figure 1. But who cares? Power is generated not under open circuit conditions, but at high currents and lower voltages. Engineers are interested in power not OCVs.

Fuel cells were studied on this intellectual base. Material problems and the lack of clean hydrogen kept the fuel cell on the shelf for a century. After the invention of the dynamo by Siemens, power was generated with rotating shafts of steam engines, internal combustion motors, water wheels and steam turbines. There was no need to fabricate clean hydrogen for power generation with electrochemical devices. Fuel cells were listed, if at all, as foot notes in compendiums of science and engineering. In fact, the word “fuel cell” cannot be found on any of the 45 index pages of the 3,600 page “Handbook of Chemistry and Physics” (student edition) of 1963.

Figure 1 Current understanding of proton-conducting fuel cells

In the sixties of the past century fuel cells were revived as power sources for space vehicles. Unfortunately, the theoretical base developed before 1900 and mentioned in various text books was not critically reviewed. Understanding of physics had improved during the dormant period of fuel

cells, but the new evidence was not used to explain the fundamental processes in proton-conducting fuel cells. A number of key points have been overlooked. Recently, the fuel cell analysis was critically revised [2]. The theory is now based on today’s understanding of elementary physics and experimental evidence. The key points of this revision are now presented.

2. Cell Reactions

Since invention of the proton-conducting fuel cells the ordinary oxidation of hydrogen to water was considered and used for theoretical considerations. An open circuit voltage of 1.23 V was predicted for this elementary reaction. However, this voltage has never been experimentally verified. A closer look at the physics, Figure 2, reveals that the fuel cell effect is a combination of three processes, two leading to electrochemical potentials (grey fields). The products of these two reactions are chemically combined to water (yellow field) without any contribution to the cell voltage. All three processes of importance occur at the cathode.

At the anode hydrogen molecules are conditioned by platinum for the transfer across the electrolyte. The protons arriving at the cathode may either recombine to hydrogen molecules or partially oxidize to hydroxyl ions. Both electrochemical reactions are illustrated in Fig. 2 on gray fields. Protons arriving at the cathode are shifted by one or two polarity changes. In the recombination case two protons will recombine at the cathode to hydrogen molecules. Two protons are shifted over one polarity change step from the anode (negative) to neutral. In case of hydrogen partial oxidations one proton is shifted over two polarity changes from anode (negative) via neutral to cathode (positive).

Figure 2 Electrochemical and chemical PEM fuel cell reactions

The number of polarity changes has not yet been considered in the analytical treatment of PEM fuel cells. At the cathode oxygen molecules are apparently split by pairs of hydrogen radicals for the

formation of hydroxyl ions. No catalysts are needed for this “ORR” oxygen reduction reaction. In the yellow “end zone” platinum will split hydrogen molecules again. Two hydrogen radicals combine with two hydroxyl radicals to water. This chemical reaction does not contribute to the voltage formation of the PEM fuel cell.

2.1 Anode

Apparently, the hydrogen dissociation on platinum at the anode (negative for fuel cells) is just an enabling reaction for the proton transport across the electrolyte.

Hydrogen molecules are split on platinum and become hydrogen radicals H•. Protons are formed when hydrogen radical release their electron. They migrate across the proton-conducting electrolyte to the cathode where they pick up an electron and become hydrogen radicals again.

2.2 Cathode

As Schoenbein had already postulated, the fuel cell effect is based on cathodic reactions. At the electrolyte-cathode interface protons pick up electrons and become hydrogen radicals again. Figure 2 illustrates that there are three reactions to be considered inside the cathode (positive for fuel cells) chamber: Hydrogen recombination, hydrogen partial oxidation and the chemical combination of the products of the two electrochemical reactions to water.

2.2.1 Hydrogen Recombination

This hydrogen recombination reaction is shown in the upper grey section of Figure 2. Even in the absence of platinum the two protons (H⁺) will combine with two electrons (e⁻) to form two hydrogen radicals (H•) that then unite to one hydrogen molecule.

Under standard conditions this **recombination reaction** results in an observable equilibrium potential of 1.053 V (see analysis below). Two electrons participate in this reaction. In the voltage space they are shifted over one polarity change step from negative at the anode to neutral polarity at the cathode. Normally the word “cathode” suggests a positive polarity with respect to the anode. In the voltage space, however, a neutral potential level is placed between positive and negative polarity, i.e. between anode and cathode. This has so far been overlooked. This combination reaction is exothermic.

To my knowledge the recombination reaction has never been considered although the resulting equilibrium potential of 1.053 V is close to the observed open circuit voltage of proton conducting fuel cells. Molecular hydrogen has been found at the cathode, but attributed to hydrogen leakage across the electrolyte or “hydrogen cross-over”. As the recombination of hydrogen radicals does not need any catalytic assistance, it should be possible to demonstrate an equilibrium potential of 1.053 V with no platinum at the cathode. The pressure inside the cathode chamber should be kept low to remove the hydrogen gas generated by merging hydrogen radicals. Heat is released by this reaction.

2.2.2. Hydrogen Partial Oxidation

The partial oxidation of hydrogen is shown in the lower grey section of Figure 2. Platinum is needed inside the cathode chamber for either splitting the hydrogen molecules already formed by

recombination or for preventing their formation. Apparently, oxygen molecules provided to the cathode environment are split by hydrogen radicals (H⁺) and hydroxyl radicals (HO[•]) are formed.

New evidence

As shown in Figure 2, protons are shifted over two polarity change steps from negative (anode) via neutral to positive (cathode). The number of polarity step changes has not been included in the standard equilibrium potential equation (see below). In the voltage space, the potential shift steps are two from positive via neutral to negative as illustrated in Figure 2, and not a simple polarity sign change as commonly assumed. The partial oxidation reaction is exothermic. However, heat is needed to dissociate the oxygen molecule.

This **partial oxidation reaction** is associated with a second equilibrium potential of 0.876 V (see below). This voltage cannot be experimentally observed because it is hidden by the higher voltage of the recombination reaction. However it can be retrieved on the voltage axis by backward projections of the linear parts of voltage-current dependences.

2.2.3 Reaction Product Disposal

The third reaction shown in the yellow filed of Figure 2 is the chemical disposal of the products of the first two electrochemical reactions. Two hydroxyl radicals combine with two hydrogen radicals to two water molecules.

New evidence

This reaction is not involved in the transfer of protons across the electrolyte. It is truly a chemical combination of the products of the two voltage-forming reactions inside the cathode chamber as illustrated by Figure 2. Consequently, it does not contribute to the cell voltage. However, this exothermic reaction is the main contributor of heat reeleased during operation of PEM fuel cells.

3. Equilibrium Potential Formation

Energy is needed to displace an electric charge in an electric field. Faraday proposed the following equation that has been used to predict the equilibrium potentials (EP) of fuel cells since then.

$$\text{EP(V)} = -\Delta G F^{-1} n_e^{-1} \quad (5)$$

According to this equation the equilibrium voltage potential EP is obtained by dividing the Gibbs free energy ΔG (J/mol) by the product of the Faraday constant $F = 96'600$ (A s mol⁻¹) and the number n_e of electrons involved in the transfer process.

Unfortunately, this equation is incomplete. Normally, the protons are shifted by a single polarity change step, e.g. from plus or minus to neutral. In the case of proton conducting fuel cells, they are shifted for recombination by one polarity step and for partial oxidation by two polarity steps (*new evidence*) from negative via neutral to positive as illustrated by Figure 2.

The number of polarity changes n_p assigned to the shift of protons in the voltage space is also true for the participating electrons. The completed equilibrium potential equation thus equation becomes

New evidence

$$EP(V) = -\Delta G F^{-1} n_e^{-1} n_p^{-1} \quad \text{Completed equilibrium potential equation} \quad (6)$$

For fuel cells with acidic electrolytes we have $n_e = 2$ and $n_p = 1$, while for the recombination reaction (partial oxidation) $n_e = 1$ and $n_p = 2$. For solid oxide, molten carbonate or alkaline fuel cells $n_p = 1$. The equilibrium potentials mentioned above are based on the revised EP equation (6). Under standard conditions an equilibrium potential of 1.053 V is predicted for the recombination reaction. The equilibrium potential for partial oxidation is 0.876 V and cannot be experimentally observed, because it is hidden under the recombination voltage and thus not accessible for experimental verification.

4. Equilibrium Potentials

The equilibrium potential can now be obtained for hydrogen recombination and hydrogen partial oxidation. The following equilibrium voltages are predicted for standard conditions by eq. 6:

4.1 Hydrogen Recombination:

In the case of hydrogen recombination (eq. 2) two electrons ($n_e = 2$) are shifted over one polarity step change ($n_p = 1$). For the recombination reaction $2H^+ \Rightarrow H_2$ the Gibbs Free Energy ΔG is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G_{H^+} &= 203.278 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1} && \text{Gibbs Free Energy of hydrogen radicals [6]} \\ \Delta G_{H_2} &= 0 && \text{Gibbs Free Energy of hydrogen molecules [6]} \\ \Delta G &= \Delta G_{H^+} - 2 \Delta G_{H_2} = -406.556 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1} - 0 = -406.556 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1} \end{aligned}$$

With the Faraday constant $F = 96.485 \text{ C mol}^{-1}$ the electrochemical potential for hydrogen recombination becomes

New evidence

$$EP_{\text{rec}}(V) = -\Delta G [F n_e n_p]^{-1} = -(-406.556 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}) (96.485 \text{ C mol}^{-1} 2 \times 1)^{-1} = 1.053 \text{ V} \quad (7)$$

4.2 Hydrogen Partial Oxidation:

For the hydrogen partial oxidation reaction $2(H^+) + 2(O^{2-}) \Rightarrow 2(HO^-)$ the exchange of Gibbs Free Energy ΔG is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G_{H^+} &= 203.278 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1} && \text{Gibbs Free Energy of hydrogen radicals [6]} \\ \Delta G_{O_2} &= 0 && \text{Gibbs Free Energy of oxygen molecules [6]} \\ \Delta G_{OH^-} &= 34.277 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1} && \text{Gibbs Free Energy of hydroxyl [6]} \\ \Delta G &= 2\Delta G_{OH^-} - 2\Delta G_{H^+} - \Delta G_{O_2} = 68.554 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1} - 406.556 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1} - 0 = -338.002 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1} \end{aligned}$$

With the Faraday constant $F = 96.485 \text{ C mol}^{-1}$, $n_e = 2$ and $n_p = 2$ the electrochemical potential for hydrogen partial oxidation becomes

New evidence

$$EP_{\text{oxi}}(V) = -\Delta G [F n_e n_p]^{-1} = -(-338.002 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}) (96.485 \text{ C mol}^{-1} 2 \times 2)^{-1} = 0.876 \text{ V} \quad (8)$$

5. Characteristics

In both processes (recombination and partial oxidation) protons experience the same area-specific resistance AsR . However, we have to deal with two voltage-current characteristics for recombination and oxidation. Initially 2/3 of the protons contribute to hydrogen recombination and 1/3 to hydrogen oxidation.

New evidence

$$U_{\text{rec}} \text{ (V)} = EP_{\text{rec}} - \text{AsR} (\Omega \text{ cm}^2) \frac{2}{3} i \text{ (A cm}^{-2}\text{)} \quad \text{recombination} \quad (9)$$

$$U_{\text{oxi}} \text{ (V)} = EP_{\text{oxi}} - \text{AsR} (\Omega \text{ cm}^2) \frac{1}{3} i \text{ (A cm}^{-2}\text{)} \quad \text{oxidation} \quad (10)$$

Both fuel cell reactions follow the Ohmic law. As shown in Figure 3 the cell voltages are linearly diminished by the area-specific Ohmic resistance (AsR) of the cell system. The slopes of the two falling lines are determined by the current flow associated with the exchange processes. Two protons are consumed when hydrogen radicals are recombined to molecules. But only one proton is involved in the partial oxidation of hydrogen to hydroxyl. Consequently, the slope of the hydrogen recombination line is twice that for hydrogen oxidation.

The observed U-i-dependences are schematically shown in red, Figure 3. Under open circuit conditions and immediately thereafter the recombination voltage near the equilibrium potential of 1.053 V is observed. For partial oxidation the equilibrium potential of 0.876 V cannot be experimentally displayed, because it is hidden under the recombination potential. However, it can be retrieved on the voltage axis by the intersection of the extrapolated straight voltage line obtained for higher current densities.

The two voltage-current lines will not intersect with each other, but smoothly merge with increasing current density as indicated by the red transition line in Figure 3. This merger is presumably of exponential nature as the input depends on the output of previous reactions.

Figure 3 Schematic U-i-dependence of hydrogen recombination and oxidation at the cathode

The red transition line illustrates the exponential merger of the hydrogen recombination line with the dominating partial hydrogen oxidation curve of proton-conducting fuel cells.

New evidence

$$U(i) = U_{\text{oxi}} + \Delta U(i) = EP_{\text{oxi}} i \text{ AsR} + (EP_{\text{rec}} - EP_{\text{oxi}}) \exp[- 2 \varphi i \text{ AsR} (EP_{\text{rec}} - EP_{\text{oxi}})^{-1}] \quad (11)$$

Under standard conditions at 25°C the voltage-current characteristic becomes

$$U(i) = 0.876V i \text{ AsR} + 0.177V \exp[- 2 \varphi i \text{ AsR} (0.177V)^{-1}] \quad (12)$$

Variable voltages are marked by “U” and current densities by “i”. AsR stands for the measureable area-specific-resistance of the cell. The factor “2” in the argument of the experimental term accounts for higher current flow of the recombination compared to the oxidation process. A fitting parameter φ is used to account for system-specific features affecting the exponential decay, such as contact resistance between electrodes and bipolar plates or insufficient cathode exhaust rates. Equation 11 may be the first closed formulation presented for the voltage-current relationship in the “polarization region” of PEM fuel cells.

6. Experimental Verification

In Figure 4, the presented analysis is verified by comparison with experimental results obtained by Harel et al. [3] for a 42 cell PEM stack of 5 kW nominal output. The experimental evidence obtained with a tall and powerful stack is less likely to be affected by systematic experimental errors. At the low single cell voltages and at high cell currents it is difficult to make measurements accurate as they may be affected by Ohmic resistance of cables, connections and instruments. Based on the single cell potential of 1.053 V, the electrochemical potential of the tall stack should be 44.2 V. This is excellent agreement with Harel’s reported results.

The area-specific resistance ($0.456 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$) of the Harel experiment was taken from the slope of the original experimental data and reproduced in Figure 4. The theoretical equilibrium potentials presented for recombination and oxidation above were used a starting points. In the “polarization region” the exponential transition depends on a number of experimental parameters such a conductivity of current collector, contact resistance between bipolar plates and electrolyte etc. These effects are summarized by a fitting parameter $\varphi = 10$ in Eq. 11. Based on this input the results of the voltage-current equations (11) are compared to the reported results of the of the Harel experiment. The agreement is excellent as shown in Figure 4. A perfect agreement is obtained when the temperature of 55°C reported by Harel is also used for the analytical prediction as illustrated by the solid red line.

Figure 4 Experimental results obtained by Harel (dots) are compared to results of this analysis. Perfect agreement is achieved when theory and experiments are based on the same temperature (solid red line).

7 Conclusions

This compact presentation of the recently published modification [2] of the fuel cell theory illustrates that some theoretical interpretations echoed for 190 years need to be updated. Since Schoenbein's discovery of the fuel cell effect scientists have accepted rudimentary explanations, searched for experimental evidence and developed complex theories to explain the poor match of experimental results. The revised analysis summarized here appears to correctly describe the physical effects leading to the voltage generation in "polarization region" of proton-conducting fuel cells. A complete analysis is presented in the recent publications of the author [1] and [2].

8. Recommendations

Based on the presented analysis the voltage-current dependence of proton-conducting fuel cells can be accurately described by a single equation (11). Consequently, the following advices should now be given:

- A Stop searching for an equilibrium potential (EP) of 1.23 V. Hydrogen recombination leads to an EP of 1.053 V while hydrogen partial oxidation results in an EP of 0.876 V. This EP is hidden under the recombination line and cannot be observed experimentally.
- B Stop searching for four electrons. Two electrons are shifted over two polarity change steps in the dominating hydrogen partial oxidation reaction. Two times two equals four.
- C Stop searching for catalysts for a cathodic oxygen reduction reaction (ORR). Oxygen molecules are split by pairs of hydrogen radicals and two hydroxyl radicals are formed in the process. This reaction does not need catalytic support.
- D Platinum is needed in the anode chamber to split hydrogen molecules to protons for the transfer of across the electrolyte. This anodic reaction is not part of the fuel cell reaction inside the cathode chamber, but necessary for the transport of hydrogen to the cathode across the proton-conducting electrolyte.
- E Platinum is not needed in the cathode chamber for the hydrogen recombination reaction, but needed for the partial oxidation reaction to dissociate hydrogen molecules created by recombination or to prevent their formation.

The physical model used to describe the oxidation of hydrogen in protonic fuel cells needs to be corrected. This communication is an improved update of an analysis published by the author recently [1] and in the International Journal of hydrogen Energy [2].

8. References

- [1] Ulf Bossel: Fuel Cells – From Birth to Maturity, Springer Synthesis Lectures on Engineering, Science, and Technology, ISBN 978-3-031-44538-5 (2024)
- [2] Ulf Bossel: OCV Mystery Solved for Proton-Conducting Fuel Cells? International Journal of Hydrogen Energy, Vol. 47, Issue 15, (February 2022)
- [3] Harel et al.: Proc. 2nd European PEFC Forum, Lucerne 2003, page 507 (2003)

There are many attempts (e.g. Butler-Volmer, Heyrovsky etc.) to solve the “open circuit puzzle” of PEM fuel cells, but none of them has produced solution sufficiently meaningful to be cited in this publication. All of them have based their analysis on the historic assumption that there is only one fuel cell reaction, namely the chemical hydrogen-oxygen combination to water. Also, the two-step polarity shift has never been considered. Since the discovery of the fuel cell effect science has searched “for the needle in the wrong hay stack”. Therefore, this communication does not include a critical review of the published speculative assumptions, but presents an analysis based on a corrected physical model and supported by experimental evidence.

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